

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Post-trial access practice in malaria, tuberculosis, and NTDs clinical trial studies in Sub-Saharan African countries, quantitative study

[version 1; peer review: 2 not approved]

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Abstract

Background

According to CIOMS, 2016 post-trial access (PTA) refers to the ethical imperative that requires the sponsor, researchers, and relevant public health authority, "to make available as soon as possible any intervention or product developed, and knowledge generated, for the population or community in which the research is carried out."

PTA is stipulated and recommended by different international research guidelines like CIOMS, and it was acknowledged that PTA should be accessible to those who actively participated in the trial study and the community and/or host country. Law, policy, and practical guidance for PTA has so far been vague but has recently attracted and increased attention in the context of benefit sharing of scientific research results with low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).

Even though the number of clinical trials conducted in the Sub-Saharan countries has increased in the past two decades, PTA plan

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and practice is underreported or very low.

Objective

to evaluate PTA plan and implementation practice on TB, Malaria and NTD clinical trial studies conducted in the sub-Saharan African countries.

Method

a quantitative, cross sectional study survey approach is used to evaluate the PTA plan and practice of PI, trial coordinators, and sponsors in Sub-Saharan African countries.

Finding

misunderstanding of the term PTA, lack of plan, discussion, and arrangement on PTA between research stakeholders.

Conclusion

PTA training should be prepared and facilitated for researchers, IRB members, PIs, funders, and sponsors; discussion and arrangement on PTA should be done before the conduct of the trial; and there should be written agreement between the parties to guarantee PTA to study participants and community after the end of the trial study.

Keywords

post-trial access, clinical trial, TB, Malaria, NTDs

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The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

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Introduction

Background

Clinical trials are research studies performed in people aimed at evaluating a medical, surgical, or behavioral intervention. They are the primary way that researchers find out if a new treatment, like a new drug or diet or medical device (for example, a pacemaker) is safe and effective in people (Vulcano, 2017). Often a clinical trial is used to learn if a new treatment is more effective and/or has less harmful side effects than the standard treatment (NIH, 2023).

Most of the time clinical trials are conducted to test the safety and efficacy of new drugs, vaccines, medical devices, to test shorter duration of treatment, test a new dosage regimen, minimize side effects, optimize efficacy and safety, before or after marketing authorization (Fekadu *et al.*, 2014).

Clinical trials in Ethiopia and other African nations can be considered to be in their embryonic stages. The share of studies registered from Africa is (in Clinicaltrials.gov) updated as of June 2017 is only 0.025%, although the region represents about 15% of the population of the world (Fekadu *et al.*, 2014).

Within Africa, most of the clinical trials are conducted in South Africa (47.3%), which makes one of the largest financial investments on health and has a relatively well-developed health system. Only a limited number of clinical trials are registered from Ethiopia in trial registration sites, representing only 1.5% of all the studies from Africa (Pratt *et al.*, 2012).

Post-trial access (PTA) refers to the ethical imperative that requires the sponsor, researchers, and relevant public health authority, “to make available as soon as possible any intervention or product developed, and knowledge generated, for the population or community in which the research is carried out (Clinical trial in marketing authorization, 2013) not to mention to research participants who still need the intervention (Declaration of Helsinki, 2013).

The PTA should be planned and documented in the study protocol. The execution plan should be reviewed and updated during the course of the clinical trial. PTA has various aspects. First, it refers to the provision of both knowledge and intervention, if any. Second, it refers to the potential beneficiaries, which could be research participants and/or the intended patient group in the community and/or country. Third, PTA provision to research participants must be free of charge, while PTA for the community and/or host country usually comes in the form of availability and accessibility of the medicinal product within a reasonable time.

Access to an investigational intervention is justified by the principle of beneficence, “which requires researchers and sponsors to safeguard the health of participants when it is in their power to do so.” It is also supported by the principle of distributive justice: participants, and by extension the community or host country, assist researchers in generating

valuable data and, in return, researchers should ensure that participants receive needed care to safeguard their health.

Even though the number of clinical trials in LMICs has increased dramatically (Van Roessel *et al.*, 2019), with most of the trials being funded, sponsored, or otherwise influenced by private or public entities from high-income countries, the lack of PTA introduces the risk of exploiting study participants in low and middle-income countries who otherwise have limited access to healthcare.

In this case, national ethics committees and the relevant drug regulation agencies must ensure that PTA is in place. While there is limited practical experience on PTA in clinical trials in LMICs, the concept of benefit-sharing, which acts as the theoretical foundation of PTA, is firmly stipulated in different international ethical guidelines.

The UNESCO Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights, for example, highlights the duty of benefit-sharing pertaining to scientific and technological innovations, in particular with developing countries (Chirac & Torrelee, 2006; UNESCO, 2009);

The Declaration of Helsinki requires the sharing of benefits in medical research with the vulnerable group (Declaration of Helsinki, 2013); and the CIOMS International Ethical Guidelines requires multi-stakeholder cooperation to make the studied intervention and the knowledge gained available to the population or community (CIOMS, 2016).

Hence, ethical guidelines are clear that PTA, in the form of concrete plans and procedures for benefit-sharing and access (may it be in the form of reasonable pricing of an approved indication in the host country, free medicinal product for research participants, the provision of knowledge to the relevant patient population and the community), must be intrinsic to clinical trial planning. Despite these ethical guidelines, the general status quo of PTA is not encouraging: the provision of PTA is “rather the exception than the rule” (Jimenez *et al.*, 2019; Schippe, 2015).

In line with the above principles, this manuscript will explore PTA planning and implementation on TB, Malaria, and NTD clinical trials in Sub-Saharan African countries.

Methods

Study design

The study is a descriptive cross-sectional study. Cross-sectional surveys were used to explore PTA planning and implementation on TB, Malaria, and NTD clinical trials in Sub-Saharan African countries.

Study setting

The study was conducted by sending emails with a link to the online survey questionnaires to respondents who either conduct/have conducted clinical trials in sub-Saharan countries.

Sample and sampling strategy

The study respondents were principal investigators (PI), Co-PI, sponsors, researchers, and clinical trial coordinators conducting clinical trial research in TB, Malaria, and NTDs in sub-Saharan African countries. Purposive sampling was used to select the study sample. The researchers collected 300 study respondents' contact information from two clinical trial study registry sites namely called clinical trials.gov and Pan African clinical Trial registry (PACTR). The study questionnaire was sent to all the 300 study respondents, only 37 respondents completed the questionnaire.

Data collection tool and procedures

A close ended survey questionnaire was developed based on the objective of the study; to know their role in clinical trials, to explore PTA plans, and respondents' need for PTA training. The survey questionnaire was pre-tested amongst AHRI researchers for its clarity and distributed to the study participants through their email. Initially, a longer questionnaire with 17 questions on socio-demographics, PTA knowledge, PTA plans, discussions and arrangements, PTA implementation, stakeholder involvement, trial products, and roles was sent out. Unfortunately, the response rate was low and as such we shortened the questionnaire to encourage study participation. Responses were saved on the AHRI server.

Data management and analysis

("StataSE 18") was used to perform descriptive statistics in the form of frequencies and percentages, on anonymous data to maintain participants confidentiality ("Stata 18 software,"). The Fisher's exact test used to assess the associations between categorical variables. The findings are presented in tables and graphically. We considered p-values less than 0.05 as statistically significant. Though we used STATA version 18 software, we shared the dataset with Excel sheet- which can be used to perform similar descriptive analysis, or it can be exported to other freely available statistical software's like R. The R- or R Studio software is freely alternative available software that can be downloaded to most operating systems including Microsoft Windows, Linux, Mac OS, used to replicate the study result ("R Core Team (2021)R:," ; "RStudio Team (2020),").

Ethical considerations

This study received ethical approval from the Armauer Hansen Research Institute (AHRI) and the All-African Tuberculosis, Leprosy Treatment, Rehabilitation, and Training Centre (AHRI/ALERT IRB) with approval reference number PO/43/20 dated on 21/01/2021. Additionally, the Ministry of Education (MOE) National Ethical Review Board (NERB) of Ethiopia granted approval with reference number MOSHE/RD/04/246/84/21 dated on 10/06/2021. The study also got renewal for approval from the Ministry of Education (MOE) National Ethical Review Committee of Ethiopia with the reference number of MOSHE/RD/03/246/505/22 dated on 08/06/2022. Written informed consent was obtained from all study participants prior to their participation in the study. Within the

data collection procedures, the applicant strictly maintained the participant's confidentiality by using the study code number as identification for each participant for anonymity.

Results

Characteristics of the study population

Three hundred potential study participants were invited to participate in the study survey questionnaires. As illustrated in "Table 1", Thirty-seven study participants gave a complete response to the survey questionnaires given. Out of the 37% study participants, principal investigators were 21 (56.8%), sponsors were 4 (10.8%), study coordinators were 12 (32.4%), with majority of participants being based in sub-Saharan Africa (56.8%).

Majority of the respondents were from sub-Saharan Africa as indicated by "Figure 1". Most of the principal investigators (76.2%) were from Africa. Sponsors were equally distributed between collaboratives and not based in Africa. Africa and not based in Africa contributed 41.7% of the study coordinators each with the rest being collaborative study coordinators.

From those, 70% of them conducted single centered clinical trial while 30% of the respondents conducted multi-center clinical trials in the sub-Saharan African countries as indicated by Figure 2.

As shown by Figure 3, 57% and 75% of the principal investigators and study coordinators were from universities respectively, whereas all sponsors were from pharmaceutical companies.

Post-trial access plans and arrangements

Respondents were asked whether they provided PTA plans, discussions or arrangements were made in their clinical trials and if yes, in what form. A total of 21 (56.8 %) study participants stated that they provided PTA plans, discussions, or arrangements. Of the 37 study participants, 21 (56.8%) provided varying responses on PTA plans, discussions, and arrangements (Figure 4). Ten study participants representing 27.1% of the sample population said that PTA was addressed in the form of meetings and dissemination of study findings, 4 (11%) had plans to provide PTA in the form of preferential price or freely, 2 (5.4%) replied that provision of PTA is task of the IRB or the regulatory authorities while a further 2 (5.4 %) said that PTA was not provided because the product (medication for acute malaria) was available in the host country. Our findings also showed that 1 respondent (2.7%) said that they will make study data available, 1 (2.7%) replied that PTA was provided in the form of access to the medicinal product by the community and another respondent said that they would provide money as PTA. However, 16 (43.2%) of the participants responded that there was no discussion and arrangements made on PTA related to trial studies conducted

Table 1. Distribution of the study participants stratified by their roles (N = 37).

	Role of study participants			Total	P-value
	Principal investigator	Sponsor	Study co-ordinator		
Lead institute					0.01
Pharmaceutical company/ Partners	3 (33.3)	4 (44.4)	2 (22.2)	9 (24.3)	
Public Health/ Research Institute	6 (85.7)	0 (0.0)	1 (14.3)	7 (18.9)	
University	12 (57.1)	0 (0.0)	9 (42.9)	21 (56.8)	
Funder					0.07
LSHTM	2 (28.6)	0 (0.0)	5 (71.4)	7 (18.9)	
Others	19 (63.3)	4 (13.3)	7 (23.3)	30 (81.1)	
Origin					0.02
Africa	16 (76.2)	0 (0.0)	5 (23.8)	21 (56.8)	
Collaborative	2 (33.3)	2 (33.3)	2 (33.3)	6 (16.2)	
Not based in Africa	3 (30.0)	2 (20.0)	5 (50.0)	10 (27.0)	
Site					0.13
Multi-center	5 (45.5)	3 (27.3)	3 (27.3)	11 (29.7)	
Single-Center	16 (61.5)	1 (3.9)	9 (34.6)	26 (70.3)	
PTA arrangement					0.72
Yes	12 (57.1)	3 (14.3)	6 (28.6)	21 (56.8)	
No	9 (56.3)	1 (6.3)	6 (37.5)	16 (43.2)	
PTA training					0.46
Yes	13 (50.0)	3 (11.5)	10 (38.5)	26 (70.3)	
No	8 (72.7)	1 (9.1)	2 (18.2)	11 (29.7)	

on malaria, Tuberculosis or NTDs in Sub-Saharan African countries. The findings demonstrate that planning and provision of PTA is neglected even though the number of clinical trial studies conducted in the sub-Saharan Africa countries has been steadily increasing with in the last two decades.

PTA training needs

Study participants were asked if they required PTA training. Twenty-six respondents (70.3%) are willing to attend training on PTA arrangements for future clinical trial studies. However, 6 respondents (16.2%) were not willing to attend PTA training while 5 respondents (13.5%) did not declare their interest for the PTA training. Thus, most of the respondents are willing to learn about PTA arrangements and implementation. As indicated by “Figure 5”, Most of the PIs

(61.9%), sponsors (75%) and study coordinators (83.3%) stated that they would like to receive PTA training.

Discussion

The findings of this study are interesting since though the majority of the participants declared consideration of PTA, only 10% said that dissemination of knowledge is considered, only 11% said that differential pricing is considered (i.e., PTA as community availability and accessibility), and only 2.7% said that PTA will be provided in the form of access of the medicinal product to the community (what this meant is not exactly clear, i.e., whether the medicinal product will be made accessible freely or if the meaning is the same as the previous group of making the medicinal product accessible via differential pricing). These are bleak numbers but is very much

Figure 1. Stacked bar graph showing the distribution of key roles by origin.

Figure 2. Distribution of the study participants by site (N=37).

reflective of earlier findings such as that of Bernabe, *et al.* where PTA was declared by the majority of clinical trial PIs, though a closer look at their responses showed that there was no

PTA in the form of access to the medicinal product by either the research participants or the community and/or host country (Jimenez *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 3. Stacked bar graph showing the distribution of key roles by lead institutions.

Figure 4. Distribution of the responses of PTA plans, discussion or arrangements made.

The PTA plan should be requested by IRB members during the review process of trial documents. The fact that PTA

remains an exception than the rule among the participants point to the direction that this is not the case. That there is no

Figure 5. Clustered bar graph showing the distribution of key roles of the study participants by PTA.

pan-African (or international) platform to follow up on whether researchers implement their PTA plans once the research is completed makes oversight difficult.

In the case of at least some if not most of the Sub-Saharan countries, the absence of regulation and follow-up on the implementation process of PTA presents a significant challenge to its feasibility. The challenges related to PTA stem from a lack of knowledge, mutual agreement, and commitment from those responsible for ensuring the rights, safety, and well-being of study participants and the community.

Addressing these challenges can be achieved through PTA training for researchers, sponsors, and IRB members to update their perspectives on PTA and to consider it in the protocol development and review process. Active participation by research stakeholders in the planning, process, and implementation of PTA can maximize its feasibility in the region and help ensure the rights and benefits of research participants and their communities/countries.

Limitations

First, the low response rate from selected study participants and the trials they represented hindered our ability to evaluate whether the studies considered had plans for the provision and implementation of PTA. As a result, we could not conclude whether the selected trial studies had a PTA plan and implementation strategy in place before the trial was conducted.

Second, the incomplete response rate on the survey questionnaires was one of the main challenges we faced in analyzing and evaluating the relationship between the planning and

implementation of PTA practices in selected clinical trial studies in Sub-Saharan African countries.

Conclusion and recommendations

Training on PTA should be provided to research stakeholders to fill the knowledge gap. The research guidelines of each country should be amended to include a PTA plan and ensure access to study participants and communities who need the medicinal product. Additionally, distributive justice and beneficence require that there should be a mutual agreement between the researcher, funder, sponsor, and host country to provide PTA to the study participants and communities.

Data availability

The data for this article consists of bibliographic references, which are included in the References section.

Zenodo: Post-trial access practice in Malaria, Tuberculosis, and NTDs Clinical Trial studies in Sub-Saharan African countries, quantitative study. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13752053>

- Figure 1. Stacked bar graph showing the distribution of key roles by origin.
- Figure 2 Distribution of the study participants by site.
- Figure 3. Stacked bar graph showing the distribution of key roles by lead institutions.
- Figure 4. Distribution of the responses of PTA plans, discussion or arrangements made.

- Figure 5. Clustered bar graph showing the distribution of key roles of the study participants by PTA training.
- Table 1. Distribution of study participants stratified by their role.
- Information sheet for study participants.
- PTA data Excel format.
- Raw data survey 1
- Raw data survey 2
- Study survey questionnaires

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license](#) (CC-BY 1.0).

Authors contribution

1. Mrs. Yemisrach Zewdie Seralegne - contributed to design, acquisition of data, analysis, and interpretation of data, wrote the first draft of the manuscript, and revised the manuscript for important intellectual content.
2. Dr. Cynthia Khamala Wangamati - contributed to conception and design, analysis, interpretation of data, reviewing and editing the manuscript critically for important intellectual content.

3. Prof. Rosemarie de la Cruz Bernabe - contributed to conception and design, analysis, and interpretation of data, reviewing and editing the manuscript critically for important intellectual content.
4. Mr. Ibrahim Mdala - contributed to analysis and interpretation of data.
5. Dr. Martha Zewdie - contributed to design, acquisition of data and revised the manuscript for important intellectual content.
6. Dr. Hawult Taye - contributed to design, acquisition of data, analysis, and interpretation of data. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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- We are grateful to all study participants.
- For the purpose of open access, the author has applied a CC0 BY public copyright license to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising from this submission.

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Richard Idro

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First, old or outdated information is used to inform the study. For example, the quote that only 0.025% of registered trials in [clinicaltrials.gov](#) come from Africa was a study published in 2014. Similarly, that nearly 50% of African studies are conducted in South Africa is based on a publication over 12 years ago. There could have been a lot of changes since then.

Secondly, it was not clear how a decision was made to invite 300 participants. Was this the required sample size? If so, the study failed badly as only 37 responses (12%) were obtained. What, therefore, is the validity of these findings? They cannot surely be representative. Moreover, even the 37 responses were based on a shorter version of the study tool, and not the initial tested questionnaire because of the poor response.

Figure 1, which attempts to give the distribution of the respondents' country uses percentages. This gives a wrong perception for such a small number. They should have used the actual numbers. Furthermore, on the validity of the results, what was the distribution of the respondents (responded and based in an African Institution vs responded and based in a non-African Institution) to understand these issues? This comparison is not given.

The methods left out a critical component: the investigators did not provide a standardized definition or criteria of what PTA in this context is. This was left for the respondents to figure out. It is unlikely that the responses all meant the same thing. Thus, the results are presented in non-uniform manner.

Potentially, the ability to provide post-trial care as such is more difficult with the PI, co-PI and study coordinators than sponsors especially if these are Pharmaceutical companies. Unfortunately, only 4 of the respondents were companies. First, what proportion out of the 300 approached were companies? Was this representative? Secondly, were the 4/37 who responded similar? Could more have provided PTA if more pharmaceutical companies provided answers?

The results section is grossly inadequate but is understandable because of the small numbers.

This study could have further been strengthened with a qualitative component.

The whole concept of PTA and the responsibilities of the different actors need to be re-examined. Many studies in Africa are investigated, and funding is sought from foundations and scientific grants or fellowships. It is grossly unfair to imagine that such should put in plans for free post-trial distribution or differential pricing, which is beyond their scope. Such a scenario can even kill innovations.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

No

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

No

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Paediatrics, Child Health, Paediatric Neurology, Clinical trials

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Reviewer Report 13 November 2024

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The authors of this paper seek to evaluate the planning and implementation of post-trial access for clinical trials related to TB, Malaria, and Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs) in sub-Saharan Africa. Post-trial access is an important part of project management that requires careful planning and fair execution. The authors should be commended for their work on this paper. However, improving the way they present and explain their research would make it stronger. They also need to be clearer about their methods and results. The paper should be revised to correct grammar and spelling mistakes and include proper references to back up their claims, especially in the 'Background' section. It's also unclear which sub-Saharan countries are part of the clinical trials included in this study, when the searches for the clinical trials took place, and what specific terms were used in those searches. It's not clear if the findings can be applied to all sub-Saharan Africa or if they represent current information.

Specific comments:

1. Title: Please consider re-phrasing the title to add... 'a quantitative study' at the end.

Abstract:

1. There are several acronyms in the abstract that haven't been defined. Please provide definitions for these upon their first use (e.g., CIOMS, TB, NTD, PI, IRB).
2. Introduction -> The introduction contains relatively long sentences. Please consider condensing this section to allow for more content in the rest of the abstract.
3. Objective -> Please ensure that the beginning of each sentence is capitalized (this applies to the 'Method' and 'Finding' subsections as well). Additionally, please specify which sub-Saharan countries are being referred to.
4. Method -> The current description is inadequate. Please provide detailed information about the quantitative methods employed and the sample sizes for each group. For instance, "We designed a questionnaire to gather information on X [list key themes]. A total of X[number of] respondents participated, including X[number of] PIs, X[number of] coordinators, etc."
5. Finding -> The information provided in this section is insufficient. Please elaborate on the findings, specifying which themes were the most common or significant. Were these themes consistent across all surveyed groups?

Background: The major comment for this section is to provide sufficient evidence/references for the claims made, particularly about the state of clinical trials in sub-Saharan countries.

1. In the third paragraph, the phrase "clinical trials in Africa are considered to be in their embryonic stages" is somewhat unclear. Does this refer to the quantity or the scale of the clinical trials being conducted in African nations? Furthermore, the citation used to support this statement is over seven years old—are there any more recent statistics available?
2. In the fourth paragraph, kindly cite the original source from which the 47.3% figure originates, along with the date it was calculated, since it is over 10 years old. Additionally, it would be helpful to clarify what is meant by a "well-developed health system." At this point, it is also unclear why the authors have specifically chosen to emphasize South Africa and Ethiopia.
3. In the fifth and sixth paragraphs, please ensure consistency in the definition of Post-trial access (PTA). In the fifth paragraph, PTA is described as "the ethical imperative," while in the sixth paragraph, it is characterized as "the provision of both knowledge and intervention" and refers to "potential beneficiaries." This inconsistency makes the definition of PTA as used by the authors somewhat ambiguous.
4. In the seventh paragraph, kindly provide references for the quotations included.

5. In the ninth paragraph, please provide references to support the assertions made, such as the claim that "there is limited practical experience on PTA in clinical trials in LMICs."

Methods:

1. This section would benefit from a clearer definition of the variables and the reasoning behind the authors' categorization, particularly those listed in Table 1: Regarding the 'lead institute' variable, the term 'Partners' in the 'Pharmaceutical company/Partners' category is vague—could the authors provide clarification? Additionally, does the lead institute refer to the participant's current location or their location during the clinical trial? What if the participant was affiliated with an associate institute or organization rather than the lead institute? Regarding the 'funder' variable, can the authors explain the decision to categorize funders as just 'LSHTM' and 'Others'? This could be due to the nature of the data, but greater transparency would be appreciated. Does the 'origin' variable pertain to the participant's place of origin, their current location, or the location they were associated with during the clinical trial? Please clarify. What does 'PTA arrangement' specifically entail? Does it refer to a planned PTA, an implemented PTA plan, or the manner of implementation of the PTA plan? What does 'PTA training' specifically refer to—does it mean a course or workshop?
2. In the study design section, the phrase 'Cross-sectional surveys were used...' implies multiple surveys—were there indeed several, and if so, could you provide an explanation?
3. In the sample and sampling strategy section, please revise the phrase 'namely called' and include references to the databases used (a website would suffice). Additionally, specify when the search was conducted, which keywords or combinations were employed in the searches, and clarify why an initial sample size of 300 was chosen.
4. In the data collection and procedure section, please define AHRI upon its first mention.
5. In the data management and analysis section, it's unnecessary to state: 'Although we used STATA version 18 software, we shared the dataset with Excel...' Furthermore, what do the authors mean by 'The Fisher's exact test was used to assess the associations between categorical variables'? What exactly do the authors mean by 'associations' in this context?

Results:

1. This section could benefit from the inclusion of a table showing the search results, detailing the number of trials found and their distribution among TB, Malaria, and NTDs, among other categories.
2. For Table 1, please refer to the first comment regarding the 'methods' section. Could you clarify what the p-values signify for lead institute, funder, origin, and site (i.e., what significant differences are being referenced, and how do these relate to the study's objectives)?
3. Regarding Figure 2, is this indicating the location of the participants? Where they were based during the clinical trial? Where the trial itself took place? Additionally, how does this relate to the research question?
4. For post-trial access plans and arrangements, it may be more effective to categorize this data more succinctly if possible—such as 'PTA plan/arrangement', 'PTA implementation', and 'no PTA'—to provide a clearer overview of engagement levels with PTA. This ties back to how the authors are defining PTA.
5. In the section on PTA training needs, the authors focus on participants' willingness to receive training rather than assessing their actual training requirements.

Discussion:

1. The conclusion that 'The challenges related to PTA stem from a lack of knowledge, mutual agreement, and commitment from those responsible for ensuring the rights, safety, and well-being of study participants and the community.' is not supported by the evidence presented in this paper. Specifically in Figure 4, more than half of respondents indicated some plan for, or implementation of PTA

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Partly

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Statistics and epidemiology, malaria, NTDs

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 24 Feb 2025

Yemisrach Seralegne

(1st) Reviewer comment and point by point response Specific comments:

C1. Title: Please consider re-phrasing the title to add... ' ; a quantitative study' at the end.

R1. Thanks for the suggestion. We have addressed this comment on page 1. Please, see the research title.

Abstract:

C1. There are several acronyms in the abstract that haven't been defined. Please provide definitions for these upon their first use (e.g., CIOMS, TB, NTD, PI, IRB).

R1. Thank you for the comment. We have addressed the comment on page 1 paragraph

1line 1, paragraph 4 line 2, paragraph 5 line 2, and paragraph 7 line 1.

C2. Introduction -> The introduction contains relatively long sentences. Please consider condensing this section to allow for more content in the rest of the abstract.

R2• Thank you for the comment. As requested, the introduction part used to have condensed sentences now. Kindly see page 2, paragraphs 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6.

C3. Objective -> Please ensure that the beginning of each sentence is capitalized (this applies to the 'Method' and 'Finding' subsections as well). Additionally, please specify which sub-Saharan countries are being referred to.

R3• The beginning of each sentence has been capitalized in the objective, method, and findings subsections as advised. In this study all sub-Saharan African countries are included.

C4. Method -> The current description is inadequate. Please provide detailed information about the quantitative methods employed and the sample sizes for each group. For instance, "We designed a questionnaire to gather information on X [list key themes]. A total of X [number of] respondents participated, including X [number of] PIs, X[number of] coordinators, etc."

R4• Detail description about the quantitative method and sample size is provided on page 4, paragraph 1,3,4 and 5 line 94 to 97, and 101 to 111.

C5. Finding -> The information provided in this section is insufficient. Please elaborate on the findings, specifying which themes were the most common or significant. Were these themes consistent across all surveyed groups?

R5. The most common themes were identified and the findings were elaborated on page 5, paragraph 2, line 160 to 175.

Background: The major comment for this section is to provide sufficient evidence/references for the claims made, particularly about the state of clinical trials in sub-Saharan countries.

R6. Sufficient and updated references have been used throughout the document.

C1. In the third paragraph, the phrase "clinical trials in Africa are considered to be in their embryonic stages" is somewhat unclear. Does this refer to the quantity or the scale of the clinical trials being conducted in African nations? Furthermore, the citation used to support this statement is over seven years old—are there any more recent statistics available?

R1 • We have deleted this sentence and used more recent statistics as advised. Kindly, see references on page 2, paragraph 2 to 4, and line 40 to 54.

C2. In the fourth paragraph, kindly cite the original source from which the 47.3% figure originates, along with the date it was calculated, since it is over 10 years old. Additionally, it would be helpful to clarify what is meant by a "well-developed health system." At this point, it is also unclear why the authors have specifically chosen to emphasize South Africa and Ethiopia.

R2 • We have deleted the whole sentence. The content of the whole paragraph has been

updated, and recent research cited results are used as a reference. Kindly see page 2, paragraphs 2, 3, and 4.

C3. In the fifth and sixth paragraphs, please ensure consistency in the definition of post-trial access (PTA). In the fifth paragraph, PTA is described as "the ethical imperative," while in the sixth paragraph, it is characterized as "the provision of both knowledge and intervention" and refers to "potential beneficiaries." This inconsistency makes the definition of PTA as used by the authors somewhat ambiguous.

R3• PTA is defined consistently throughout the manuscript. on page 2 paragraph 4, and line 51 to 54.

C4. In the seventh paragraph, kindly provide references for the quotations included.

R4• Reference for the quotations sentence is included on page3 paragraph 1 and line 64.

C5. In the ninth paragraph, please provide references to support the assertions made, such as the claim that "there is limited practical experience on PTA in clinical trials in LMICs."

R5• References is put to support the assertions made on page 3 paragraph 2 and line 67-70.

Methods: This section would benefit from a clearer definition of the variables and the reasoning behind the authors' categorization, particularly those listed in **Table 1: C1.**

Regarding the 'lead institute' variable, the term 'Partners' in the 'Pharmaceutical company/Partners' category is vague—could the authors provide clarification?

R1. Thank you, based on the given comments we remove the term from the table 1. Which is helpful to minimize bias and transfer a clear message and ideas to the readers on PTA based on the general objective of the study.

C2. Please clarify. What does 'PTA arrangement' specifically entail? Does it refer to a planned PTA, an implemented PTA plan, or the manner of implementation of the PTA plan? What does 'PTA training' specifically refer to—does it mean a course or workshop?

R2. 'PTA arrangement' term is well clarified in page 7, paragraph 4, line 209 to 211 and PTA training on line 212 to 213

C3. In the study design section, the phrase 'Cross-sectional surveys were used...' implies multiple surveys—were there indeed several, and if so, could you provide an explanation?

R3. It is typing error; we used one survey and corrected.

C4. In the sample and sampling strategy section, please revise the phrase 'namely called' and include references to the databases used (a website would suffice). Additionally, specify when the search was conducted, which keywords or combinations were employed in the searches, and clarify why an initial sample size of 300 was chosen.

R4. Why 300 sample size is clarified well on page 4, paragraph 3 line 100 to 104. When the search was conducted, and key words employed in the searches is clarified now on page 4, paragraph 4.

C5. In the data collection and procedure section, please define AHRI upon its first mention.

R5• AHRI is defined now on page 4, paragraph 5 line 3 to 4.

C6. In the data management and analysis section, it's unnecessary to state: 'Although we used STATA version 18 software, we shared the dataset with Excel...' Furthermore, what do the authors mean by 'The Fisher's exact test was used to assess the associations between categorical variables'? What exactly do the authors mean by 'associations' in this context?

R6• Noted well and corrected. The fisher's exact test ¹Fisher's exact *P*-value showing the association between the role of the participants, PTA training and trial site with PTA arrangements. For example, the association between role and PTA arrangements has a *P* = 0.72. This means that the PIs, sponsors and study coordinators were equally likely to make PTA arrangements.

Results:

C1. This section could benefit from the inclusion of a table showing the search results, detailing the number of trials found and their distribution among TB, Malaria, and NTDs, among other categories.

R1• one paragraph was prepared and included to show the search result on page 6, paragraph 2 and line 172 to 175.

C2. For Table 1, please refer to the first comment regarding the 'methods' section. Could you clarify what the p-values signify for lead institute, funder, origin, and site (i.e., what significant differences are being referenced, and how do these relate to the study's objectives)?

R2. The *P*-Values have been explained under the revised Table 1. Please note that variables like the lead institute and funder have been removed because this information was sourced from the trial registry, not the survey. The term origin has been revised to trial site for better comprehension.

C3. Regarding Figure 2, is this indicating the location of the participants? Where were they based during the clinical trial? Where the trial itself took place? Additionally, how does this relate to the research question?

R3• We apologies for the lack of clarity. The location of the participants is the place where the trial itself took place, as we tried to identify the PTA practice across the sub-Saharan African countries. Consequently, it was important to know the locations of the trials.

C4. For post-trial access plans and arrangements, it may be more effective to categorize this data more succinctly if possible—such as 'PTA plan/arrangement', 'PTA implementation', and 'no PTA'—to provide a clearer overview of engagement levels with PTA. This ties back to how the authors are defining PTA.

R4. Thanks for the suggestion, this has been amended as requested in figure 2.

C5. **In the section on PTA training needs, the authors focus on participants' willingness to receive training rather than assessing their actual training requirements.** R5. We focused on the need for PTA training not willingness. We apologize for the poor grammar.

Discussion:

C1. The conclusion that 'The challenges related to PTA stem from a lack of knowledge, mutual agreement, and commitment from those responsible for ensuring the rights, safety, and well-being of study participants and the community.' is not supported by the evidence presented in this paper. Specifically in Figure 4, more than half of respondents indicated some plan for, or implementation of PTA

R1. **Thanks for the comment, we have revised our conclusion accordingly.**

(2nd) Reviewer comments and point by point responses C1. First, old or outdated information is used to inform the study. For example, the quote that only 0.025% of registered trials in clinicaltrials.gov come from Africa was a study published in 2014. Similarly, that nearly 50% of African studies are conducted in South Africa is based on a publication over 12 years ago. There could have been a lot of changes since then. **R1. Thanks, we accepted the comment and include updated information and reference now.**

C2. Secondly, it was not clear how a decision was made to invite 300 participants. Was this the required sample size? If so, the study failed badly as only 37 responses (12%) were obtained. What, therefore, is the validity of these findings? They cannot surely be representative.

Moreover, even the 37 responses were based on a shorter version of the study tool, and not the initial tested questionnaire because of the poor response.

R2. Thanks, how a decision was made to invite 300 participants is clarified on page 4 paragraph 1. As we retrieve clinical trial studies conducted within 2008-to-2019-time frame, some of the contact information was not useful as some participants had moved on to other organizations, making it difficult to trace them and as such contributed to limiting the response rate.

C3. Figure 1, which attempts to give the distribution of the respondents' country uses percentages. This gives a wrong perception for such a small number. They should have used the actual numbers. Furthermore, on the validity of the results, what was the distribution of the respondents (responded and based in an African Institution vs responded and based in a non-African Institution) to understand these issues? This comparison is not given.

R3. We revise figure 1. Based on the comments given by the reviewers and the general objective of this study. We used the actual number to give a clear perception on the proportion of each participated country.

C4. The methods left out a critical component: the investigators did not provide a standardized definition or criteria of what PTA in this context is. This was left for the respondents to figure out. It is unlikely that the responses all meant the same thing. Thus,

the results are presented in non-uniform manner.

R4. We included a standard definition for PTA based on international research guideline references on page1, paragraph 1 and page 2, paragraph 4.

C5. Potentially, the ability to provide post-trial care as such is more difficult with the PI, co-PI and study coordinators than sponsors especially if these are pharmaceutical companies. Unfortunately, only 4 of the respondents were companies. First, what proportion out of the 300 approached were companies? Was this representative? Secondly, were the 4/37 who responded similar? Could more have provided PTA if more pharmaceutical companies provided answers?

R5. Providing PTA to trial study participants and communities is not solely the responsibility of sponsors or pharmaceutical companies; rather, it is the responsibility of all research stakeholders. Detail description on proportion of study participants is briefly written on page 4 paragraph 1.

C6. The results section is grossly inadequate but is understandable because of the small numbers. This study could have further been strengthened with a qualitative component.

R6. We have strengthened the results section of this document by incorporating details on the study population's characteristics, the PTA plan and arrangements, and the PTA training needs of study participants.

C7. The whole concept of PTA and the responsibilities of the different actors need to be re-examined. Many studies in Africa are investigated, and funding is sought from foundations and scientific grants or fellowships. It is grossly unfair to imagine that such should put in plans for free post-trial distribution or differential pricing, which is beyond their scope. Such a scenario can even kill innovations.

R7. Yes, Re-examining the concept of PTA and the responsibilities of different actors is indeed important to ensure a fair and sustainable approach. While many studies in Africa rely on funding from foundations, scientific grants, or fellowships, expecting them to implement free post-trial distribution or differential pricing may not always be feasible. However, this highlights the need for a collaborative framework where multiple stakeholders—including governments, pharmaceutical companies, and global health organizations—contribute to sustainable access solutions. A balanced approach is essential to support innovation while ensuring that trial participants and communities benefit from the research outcomes.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.